

THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS, ITS PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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Annotation. This article describes the issues of improving the modern education system, effective organization of the educational process. Also, a theoretical analysis of the problems in the way of improving the quality of education in military educational institutions, their elimination and setting the perspective is given.

Keywords: Education, worldview, upbringing, effective, modern educational process, western education, methodical significance

It is known that in the socio-economic development of the country there is a need for modern knowledge and new approaches. Therefore, in improving the quality of education, the organization of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the period, the improvement of the state educational standard and educational programs, the creation of a new generation of educational literature, the use of modern innovative pedagogical and Information Technologies, the elimination of existing problems are a guarantee of our future achievements.

Education is a continuous process aimed at the continuous formation and development of the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities in people in order to live a full life and grow spiritually harmonious. The main goal of education is to educate a person with a broad scientific worldview, deep knowledge and the skills of their application in practice. In achieving the effectiveness and feasibility of this process, first of all, it is directly related to how correctly to find the answer to the following two questions:

1. What should be taught to educators (cadets), or, in other words, What knowledge should be mastered by educators (cadets) ;
2. In order for the necessary knowledge to be quickly, easily and efficiently mastered by the trainees (cadets), it is necessary to convey them in what ways;

First, it is necessary to sort, select and analyze the necessary and significant knowledge in the world of knowledge. At the same time, it is necessary to offer such a system of knowledge to educators (cadets) that this knowledge should serve as a guarantee not only to correctly establish their own life path and wisely solve life problems, but also to become mature specialists in a particular profession.

Secondly, knowledge is of methodological importance and, through the use of new advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, expresses to educators (cadets) the need for information to be interested, attracted, encouraged by the teacher, to effectively use time and make a solid decision.

On the first issue, the following dilemma arises by itself: should education be based on the principle of "everyone should be taught everything", which is a priority in Soviet pedagogy, or the principle of "everyone should be taught the necessary knowledge" in the pragmatic spirit

of the West? The pedagogy of the former Union, in its time to make everyone literate and educated, although not deviated from the communist ideology, had already achieved some progressive achievements. But how justified is education based on this principle now? First of all, it should be noted separately that the purpose of Education did not consist in the formation of a person who mastered knowledge at the encyclopedic level. In addition, the fact that at present the range of knowledge associated with an unprecedented level of branching of Sciences has expanded at a high level, significantly increasing the chances of a person receiving and assimilating this information. In particular, the system of knowledge developed within the framework of Science also requires from a person only time and hard work in order to be fully mastered. Hence, the period itself requires a certain degree of specialization and sorting and mastering of knowledge, as well as teaching.

Such a rapid change of the era, the demand in the field of education and the requirements for current development standards necessitated how relevant the role of education is in its place. In a word, now the educational process has a greater need for the principle of “teaching all the necessary knowledge.”

Over the past period, the educational process has been based on the principles of Pedagogy of the former Union. The result was a situation that had extensive knowledge, but this assimilated knowledge did not fit much into the specifics of practical life processes, slightly moving away from its heuristic nature in relation to changed conditions. (With this, we cannot think negatively about the principles of former Union pedagogy, however, it is now evident that the party ideas and ideologies of that time prevented the development and improvement of many disciplines at a mature level by the intelligentsia and scientists of the nation). In these cases, barriers arose between theory and practice. Unfortunately, the inertia of the negative consequences of this has not yet stopped. That is, the problem is that, first of all, the involvement of an excessively large system of knowledge in the organization of the educational process, the extrasensory reference of information caused moral tension in educators (cadets) and situations of embellishment from such education in the process of Education. In most cases, in the face of such a wide flow of information in educators (cadets), there is a formation of a sense of hadiksirash, skepticism about the possibilities of mastering this knowledge of oneself, and, ultimately, a quick oblivion of the information received. An alternative way is to rely more on the intensity method of referring information, giving in-depth knowledge reinforced by experience and practice;

Secondly, in education, information is referenced in a more static way. That is, the knowledge given is presented as absolute truth. In most cases, no place is left for an analytical-critical attitude towards any information received in the educational institution (cadet). When the teacher explains a particular issue or topic, alternative ways of the problem being posed to the audience are not proposed. Opinions in textbooks and educational literature are taught to accept without objection. According to such a traditional approach left over from former Union pedagogy, it is assessed that negative deviation is taking place in the educators (cadet) who have expressed a critical opinion. As a result, educators (cadets) become consumers of standard, in-depth analysis, undirected and standardized knowledge, presented only in textbooks and manuals. And the teacher becomes uncompromising, not noticing any deviations from the image of the educator (cadet), whom he listens to and accepts with the arguments he gives. An alternative way is to provide information not as an absolute truth, but as a recommendation, to make it possible for the educational (cadet) to express an alternative

opinion without stimulating the spirit of distrust of existing knowledge, to conduct research on the issue under consideration from different angles and points of view, to form an analysis skill, and the results of this;

Thirdly, the main task of education is to teach the educator (Cadet) not only to arm himself with reliable knowledge, but also to think independently. Currently, the principle "who wins with a lot of knowledge" has changed to the principle "Whoever thinks correctly and rationally will succeed more." After all, the trainee (cadet) must also have the skills to be able to apply the knowledge gained in certain and complex situations. First of all, the information that is presented as each knowledge is laid down by the educational (cadet) "what significance does this knowledge have for me personally?", "in what situations can I use this knowledge?" it is necessary to create a clear picture in relation to the questions". The justification for such motivation allows for a thorough assimilation of knowledge. One of the main laws of the human psyche is that each person is more interested in information that is relevant to him. Although general issues are being considered in the course of the lesson, this should be presented in an inviolable way to the life of an individual.

The educational process should also encourage the educational (cadet) to be able to make independent and rational decisions in problematic and difficult situations, not to be afraid to take on such responsibilities, to show initiative, to teach creative thinking. Such cases are observed that one educator (cadet) gives correct and accurate answers to the questions posed from the theoretical side. But it turns out to be incompetent in terms of the correct assessment of the life problem situation and the ability to see alternative solutions, as well as the application of the theoretical knowledge mastered in certain situations when it comes to rational decision-making. Given special attention to this problem in Western education, each course process is watered with such features as preparing an individual for problem situations and teaching him not to be afraid to take responsibility. Such problematic teaching encourages activity in the educational (cadet) on the way to finding the right solution for him by looking straight at him rather than avoiding problems.

It is permissible to pay attention to the fact that there are also a number of methodological problems associated with the content of education, along with the above-mentioned problems. On the one hand, this still maintains the priority of traditional-conservative methods and technologies in the educational process, and on the other hand, the inconsistency between the form and content arising in the process of applying new pedagogical technologies introduced into the course process. The fact is that in some teachers who have been using traditional educational technologies for a long time, traditional lecture and authoritarian features remain a priority, while in some cases it is also no secret that, focusing on the attractiveness of new pedagogical Technologies, a full-fledged manifestation of content by paying more attention to the principle of curiosity of the lesson on the

From the pedagogical problems noted above, it can be concluded that education should be based on such principles as rationality, purposefulness, alternation, democratic (not liberal or authoritarian), as well as the combination of an individual approach, traditionalism and non-traditional. It is then possible to achieve the goal of educating a generation with a highly educated and intellectual potential, a firm and positive life position, expected from the tasks of Education.

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